

Contents lists available at ScienceDirect

Journal of Neonatal Nursing

journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/jnn

Nurses' experiences and perspectives on aEEG monitoring in neonatal care: A qualitative study

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ARTICLE INFO

Handling Editor: Ms L Altimier

Keywords:

aEEG
NICU nurses
Qualitative research
Seizure detection

ABSTRACT

Purpose: This study aimed to gather nurses' experiences and perspectives regarding the amplitude-integrated electroencephalogram (aEEG) monitoring system in neonatal intensive care units (NICUs) and to explore potential avenues for future improvements.

Design and Methods: This study employed a descriptive qualitative design. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with 20 nurses from the level-III NICU of a Dutch medical center. The collected interview data were analyzed using thematic analysis.

Results: Seven main themes emerged: training in aEEG monitoring, proficiency in aEEG electrode placement and pattern interpretation, usual practices of using aEEG, neonatologist-nurse cooperation on aEEG, the performance of the automated seizure detection software, the usefulness of aEEG monitoring in the NICU, and feedback about the current aEEG monitoring system.

Conclusions: Nurses confirmed that aEEG is a valuable tool for cerebral function monitoring in the NICU; however, improvements are necessary. For better utilization of aEEG in the NICU, it is recommended to enhance nurses' aEEG knowledge and skills and apply state-of-art techniques to improve the monitoring system.

Practice implications: To enhance the aEEG knowledge of NICU nurses, we suggest introducing structured training programs, conducting routine case-centered discussions, and creating readily available reference resources. To optimize the aEEG monitoring system, it is essential to incorporate innovative electrodes, provide remote accessibility, integrate advanced algorithms, and develop an intuitive graphical user interface.

1. Introduction

Infants admitted to the neonatal intensive care unit (NICU) often have a substantial risk for brain injury or dysfunction. Hence, there is a growing interest in the continuous monitoring of brain function for these vulnerable neonates, which can enable targeted brain-focused care and outcome prediction (Bonifacio and Van Meurs, 2019). One valuable tool for achieving this purpose is the amplitude-integrated electroencephalogram (aEEG), a simplified form of EEG using only two or four electrodes (Bonifacio and Van Meurs, 2019; El-Dib et al., 2023a; El-Dib et al., 2023b). The aEEG provides a time-compressed display of raw EEG

signals on a semi-logarithmic scale. When used alongside its corresponding raw EEG traces, the aEEG can aid healthcare professionals in the early detection of brain dysfunctions such as seizures, thereby enabling timely and appropriate interventions (Rakshasbhuvankar et al., 2015; Variane et al., 2017). For these reasons, the aEEG has become increasingly popular in NICUs worldwide (Bruns et al., 2017; Tao and Mathur, 2010; Wang et al., 2021).

Nurses provide around-the-clock care at the infant's bedside and are the primary users of aEEG monitors. Their experiences and perspectives on aEEG usage in the NICU can, therefore, provide unique and valuable insights into improving the current monitoring systems. Despite this,

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnn.2023.08.003>

Received 14 June 2023; Received in revised form 9 August 2023; Accepted 13 August 2023

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existing aEEG research has largely neglected this group and their viewpoints.

To address this research gap, we conducted semi-structured interviews with NICU nurses from a hospital in the Netherlands. Our primary objective was to gather the nurses' perspectives on the usefulness of aEEG monitoring in the NICU and to identify any concerns they might have regarding the current monitoring system. Based on the feedback received, we explored potential avenues for improving the aEEG monitoring system in the future. In addition, we assessed the nurses' proficiency in using aEEG monitors, including their ability to independently place electrodes and interpret background patterns, as well as their cooperation with neonatologists on aEEG usage. For example, can nurses perform the first interpretation and know when to ask for help and support from the clinicians? In doing so, we are able to determine whether additional training or support was needed for the nurses, ultimately improving the overall care in the NICU setting.

2. Methods

2.1. Study design

This study employed a descriptive qualitative approach with semi-structured individual interviews to explore nurses' experiences and perspectives on using aEEG monitoring in the NICU (Moser and Korstjens, 2018; Sandelowski, 2000; 2010). The preparation of this study was carried out in accordance with the Consolidated Criteria for Reporting Qualitative Research (COREQ) checklist (Tong et al., 2007).

2.2. Setting and participants

This study was conducted at the Neonatology department of the Wilhelmina Children's Hospital (WKZ), University Medical Center (UMC) Utrecht, The Netherlands. The WKZ is one of the ten locations that provide intensive care (IC) in the Netherlands. The IC consists of three units, each with a capacity of eight beds. These IC units are used to treat preterm infants with intensive care needs, such as extremely (<28 weeks of gestation) and very preterm (28–32 weeks of gestation) infants, very small infants with birth weight <1000 g, and infants born term with a need for cardio-respiratory support and/or intensive monitoring.

In addition, the WKZ has a temporary stopover area between the IC and medium care divisions, which is called high care (HC, also known as post-IC in some hospitals). The HC is a single unit of eight beds that provides treatments for infants that need less acute medical care and have higher weights than IC patients. However, as infants admitted to the HC are still young (e.g., very preterm infants), the HC is merged into IC in some other hospitals. Hence, this study focused on both IC and HC units.

The inclusion criteria of this study were nurses and physician assistants (PAs) from IC and HC units, as both are often present at the bedside and responsible for visually interpreting aEEG recordings. In each IC or HC unit, three or four nurses are scheduled to provide daily care for infants. In each IC unit, one or two PAs are scheduled to monitor the infants' progress and ensure continuity and quality of care. For simplicity, nurses and PAs are collectively hereafter referred to as "nurses", except when PAs need to be mentioned separately.

At the time of this study, two-channel aEEG monitoring was performed as standard care for extremely preterm infants in their first three days after birth and for any infant at risk for seizures and perioperative complications in the WKZ. The aEEG usage demands in IC units are typically much higher than in the HC unit, indicating that IC nurses usually have more experience in both aEEG application and interpretation than HC nurses.

The aEEG monitoring is performed using the BrainZ monitor (Natus Medical Inc., Seattle, WA) in the WKZ. Subcutaneous needle electrodes are used and placed over the frontal and parietal lobes (F3, F4, P3, P4). The reference electrode is placed at Cz. The monitor displays one-

(P3–P4) or two-channel (left: F3–P3, right: F4–P4) aEEG and the corresponding raw EEG traces. Automated alert software for seizure detection is built into the BrainZ monitor for clinical screening purposes. A laminated card providing typical neonatal aEEG patterns (including background activity, sleep-wake cycling, and seizure activity) is attached to each aEEG monitor for nurses as reference.

2.3. Data collection

We performed face-to-face semi-structured interviews with IC and HC nurses in May 2022 at the hospital. Based on discussions with the whole research team, an interview guide consisting of 11 points was designed to gain nurses' sociodemographic characteristics and responses to aEEG-related questions (Supplementary Table S1). After obtaining verbal informed consent from nurses, AB and XW carried out individual interviews based on the guide. Each interview lasted approximately 15–20 min and was recorded in written notes.

2.4. Data analysis

The interview data were digitally transcribed and inductively analyzed by XW and AB according to Braun and Clark's six-step thematic analysis approach, including (1) familiarising with the data, (2) initial coding, (3) identifying broader themes, (4) reviewing themes, (5) defining themes, and (6) producing the report (Braun and Clarke, 2006). To ensure trustworthiness, these steps were rigorously followed throughout the analysis. Any uncertainty or disagreements were resolved via discussion between the two researchers or via consultation with a researcher (AvdH) with expertise in qualitative analysis. All interview data were anonymized before analysis, and each nurse was allocated a participant number (e.g., N1, N2, etc.).

3. Results

Twenty participants completed the interviews (nineteen females and one male, allocated numbers: N1–N20), comprising twelve IC nurses, four HC nurses, three student nurses, and one PA. They reported a mean of 16.8 years (SD = 12.5, range: 0.3–40.0) of working as a nurse or PA, and a mean of 7.8 years (SD = 6.1, range: 0.2–20.0) of experience with aEEG.

After detailed analysis and interpretation of the interview data, we identified seven main themes. The first two themes explored the main resources that nurses could utilize to develop their competency in aEEG and how they evaluated their proficiency in this area. The next three themes discussed nurses' experiences with aEEG and the practical challenges they faced in their daily practice. Finally, the last two themes delved into nurses' perspectives and feedback regarding the use of the aEEG monitoring system in the NICU. Each theme is described in detail below, underpinned by quotes from the participants.

3.1. Training in aEEG monitoring

Nurses gained foundational knowledge on aEEG during their formal mandatory education and developed practical skills through working experience and interactions with more experienced colleagues. Furthermore, the UMC Utrecht provides e-learning courses and clinical guidelines to help nurses reinforce and update their existing knowledge regarding aEEG.

N14: "I learned about aEEG from education, e-learning, on the job, and from colleagues."

3.2. Proficiency in aEEG electrode placement and interpretation

A few nurses encountered challenges with aEEG electrode placement. This was largely due to their concerns over the use of

subcutaneous needle electrodes which could cause pain and skin infection. The implementation of aEEG for very small infants, infants with thick hair, or infants with excessive movement also posed challenges.

N12: “Application of needle electrodes is hard for very small infants (<800 g) as their heads are small or when an infant has a lot of hair as the tape does not stick.”

Regarding aEEG interpretation, almost all nurses reported difficulties, with less experienced nurses finding it more challenging. Several nurses found it hard to distinguish between artifacts and seizures, and some perceived aEEG interpretation as subjective and ambiguous. Additionally, a few nurses struggled with interpreting aEEG patterns of very small infants, such as extremely preterm infants.

3.3. Usual practices of using aEEG

Most nurses used both aEEG and corresponding raw EEG traces during their daily care work. Some of them mentioned that they checked aEEG first and then verified the results using raw EEG. Nonetheless, a few less-experienced nurses relied solely on aEEG because of its simpler interpretation compared to raw EEG.

The majority of nurses checked aEEG monitors once or twice per hour. A few nurses indicated that they always gave a glance at the aEEG monitor remotely from the nurses' station, besides performing a careful check. Nearly half of the nurses chose to adjust their checking frequency according to the infant's medical condition, with more frequent checks for those with severe illness or seizures.

N1: “I check the aEEG monitor at least twice per hour and more often if the infant is very ill.”

3.4. Neonatologist-nurse cooperation on aEEG

Neonatologists checked the aEEG monitors regularly during their shifts. Still, they would be called by the nurses for an additional consultation in case of suspected seizures or any other abnormal activities or when the nurses were uncertain about the interpretation. If seizures were diagnosed, the nurses would seek guidance from neonatologists to determine the next course of action, which might include treatment or other options. One senior nurse, who gained more experience than some neonatologists, mentioned that she only requested well-experienced neonatologists' help.

N10: “I ask for a neonatologist's support when there is automated seizure detection, when I am in doubt about the interpretation of the traces, or when there is something worrying.”

3.5. Performance of the automated seizure detection software

The most experienced nurses used the automated seizure detection software as a guide to select points of interest while examining the entire aEEG recordings. Only a few nurses immediately called a neonatologist for consultations once an alert was triggered by the seizure detection software. The rest of the nurses (together with colleagues if needed) confirmed or rejected the detections by inspecting the raw EEG traces. The seizure detection software might miss seizures or, more frequently, falsely detect seizures (i.e., non-seizure activity was alerted).

N20: “Most problems are related to falsely detected seizures rather than missed ones.”

According to nurses, false alarms were mainly associated with movement artifacts and rhythmic artifacts related to mechanical ventilation, respiratory artifacts, electrocardiograms, hiccups, and cooling. Furthermore, false detections could also be caused by incorrectly placed electrodes, poor electrode connection due to hair, or when an infant was lying on one or both parietal electrodes (P3 and/or P4). Since there were

only four electrodes used for the acquisition, some seizure activity could be missed if their origin was far away from the electrodes.

3.6. The usefulness of aEEG monitoring in the NICU

While aEEG monitoring, at the time of the study, was part of the standard care for extremely preterm infants in their first three days after birth in the WKZ, only two less experienced nurses—one HC nurse and one student nurse—believed that this was necessary. In contrast, most nurses deemed that aEEG should only be used when there are indications, given that needle electrodes could have adverse effects on the skin of vulnerable infants.

One of the most commonly mentioned indications for aEEG monitoring was seizures or suspicion thereof. According to the nurses, seizures could be caused by cerebral bleeding (e.g., intraventricular hemorrhage), perinatal asphyxia, or elevated serum bilirubin levels, and were suspected in the presence of abnormal movements or apnea (only in term infants). The aEEG monitoring was also useful during and after surgeries to detect potential hypotension, hypoxia, fluctuations in cerebral blood flow, and hyper- or hypocapnia. When brain injury was observed through another diagnostic technique, such as ultrasound, aEEG monitoring was used for observation and outcome prediction purposes.

N6: “The monitoring is especially useful for seizure detection or other clinical problems, but not necessary for extremely preterm infants in their first three days.”

3.7. Feedback about the current aEEG monitoring system

Almost all nurses expressed their dissatisfaction with the use of needle electrodes in aEEG monitoring (particularly for very small infants) and made suggestions for optimal electrode design based on their own clinical practice. Most importantly, ideal EEG electrodes should be non-invasive and made of soft, comfortable, and skin-friendly materials that are suitable to use over long periods of time.

The nurses emphasized another critical consideration: an ideal electrode should produce EEG signals of high quality and good stability. These signals should be robust against heartbeat- and respiration-induced artifacts, and the electrodes should stay in place even when the infant is highly active.

Furthermore, the optimal EEG electrodes should be easy to apply and allow accurate and consistent placement. For instance, the electrode surface could be color-coded and/or labeled with the electrode positions (e.g., F3) to ease the application process. To further simplify the application procedure, better electrode-skin contact without the need for hair shaving is also desired. Moreover, a wireless or mobile aEEG monitoring system enabling flexible recordings would be especially valuable in the busy NICU setting where the patients are relocated frequently, e.g., for a magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) examination.

N11: “Ideal electrodes should enable good connection and be non-invasive. Also, we do not want to sacrifice (the infant's) hair.”

Additionally, from several nurses' perspectives, a better aEEG monitoring system should also be compatible with other monitoring techniques such as near-infrared spectroscopy (NIRS) and existing devices (e.g., continuous positive airway pressure). The aEEG monitor should not only allow nurses to quickly record common events (e.g., seizures) in real time but also enable them to retrospectively add event markers to previous time points (especially when they are too busy to record events in real-time) or add detailed comments to a recorded event.

4. Discussion

Nurses are primary users of the aEEG monitoring system in the NICU

and are commonly present at the bedside much longer than neonatologists. With this qualitative study, we investigated nurses' experiences and opinions of aEEG monitoring in neonatal care. Here we will discuss current major problems and future directions for improvement.

4.1. Summary of current problems

Neonatal nurses' knowledge and skills in aEEG monitoring vary, and their competency in this area is mainly improved through working experience. While there are some courses and talks available, these resources often provide only fragmented information, which is insufficient for nurses to form a comprehensive understanding of aEEG knowledge.

The inadequate understanding of aEEG among nurses has resulted in a notable discrepancy between their perception of its usefulness and its actual value in certain cases. For instance, utilising aEEG monitoring as part of the standard care for extremely preterm infants during their first three days after birth in the WKZ is backed by mounting evidence that supports the important role of aEEG in predicting subsequent brain growth and long-term outcomes for this population (Benders et al., 2015; Klebermass et al., 2011; Song et al., 2015; van 't Westende et al., 2022; Wikström et al., 2012). However, most nurses are unaware of these findings in their daily work, and many even question the necessity of this practice, citing the minimal brain activity observed in these infants. This knowledge gap can ultimately affect the quality of care provided.

Furthermore, the interpretation of aEEG recordings is challenging for most nurses, especially when it comes to distinguishing between artifacts and seizure activity, as they can appear very similar (Rakshasbhuvankar et al., 2015). Although the automated seizure detection software is a valuable addition to the aEEG monitoring system currently used in the WKZ, it can sometimes incorrectly identify artifacts as seizures. Moreover, the problem of electrode misplacement further complicates the interpretation process. Additionally, aEEG interpretation is a subjective and ambiguous process that requires special expertise, which is why nurses often seek consultation from neonatologists. It is also worth noting that several less-experienced nurses rely solely on aEEG traces, which may lead to missing short seizures and misinterpreting cortical activity due to artifacts (Rakshasbhuvankar et al., 2015).

To improve the current aEEG monitoring system, nurses gave suggestions from a user experience perspective. They stated that a good aEEG monitor should be safe, easy to use, compatible with existing devices, and should provide reliable and stable long-term recordings.

4.2. Future directions

4.2.1. Building knowledge and expertise

Systematic training programs. At the time of the study, the aEEG training provided by the WKZ was experienced as infrequent and inadequate, which made it difficult for nurses to develop a comprehensive understanding of aEEG and the underlying motivations of some aEEG monitoring practices. Thus, we recommend the development of a more systematic and structured training procedure.

To cater to the varying needs of different nurses, this training procedure should consist of different types of programs targeting nurses at different stages and ages. For instance, an orientation program should be designed for beginner nurses, providing them with basic aEEG implementation skills and essential knowledge, such as identifying typical aEEG background patterns. Furthermore, ongoing training through workshops, seminars, and refresher courses is necessary to keep nurses updated with the latest research findings on aEEG, such as its role in long-term outcome prediction and application to other neonatal groups.

Regular case-based discussions. Given the subjective nature of aEEG interpretation, it is highly recommended to conduct frequent meetings to discuss several typical and ambiguous cases. These meetings provide a platform for neonatologists and nurses to visually review the newest aEEG recordings and make decisions collaboratively. Regular

discussion sessions also offer more experienced nurses and neonatologists the opportunity to share their aEEG knowledge, facilitating effective communication and cooperation among team members, ultimately leading to improved quality of care. Furthermore, such discussions help define more detailed and clearer aEEG classification criteria, which in turn enhances interpretation accuracy.

Pocketbook and in-house knowledge engine. The laminated reference card that comes with each aEEG monitor has limited utility in certain cases. It only provides typical aEEG pattern information, which may not be sufficient for nurses who require more detailed explanation and assistance when aEEG experts are absent in the NICU. To address this issue, we propose developing a pocketbook that includes detailed examples and answers to frequently asked questions. For example, a sample illustration of the aEEG background activity for an infant with hemorrhage would aid in timely diagnosis and treatment (Benavente-Fernández et al., 2015). To enhance portability, the pocketbook can be designed in an accordion fold pattern.

Furthermore, it would be beneficial to create a neonatal aEEG knowledge engine, similar to a wiki, that contains a wealth of information and resources such as electrode placement tips, sample cases, and essential literature tailored to nurses' needs. Such an engine would enable them to quickly locate the information they require, thereby improving the efficiency of care.

4.2.2. Applying state-of-art techniques

Novel electrodes. Needle electrodes are commonly used for neonatal aEEG monitoring in the WKZ as well as other hospitals, but they can cause discomfort and harm to an infant's vulnerable skin. Thus, there is a growing need for new aEEG electrodes made from comfortable materials and suitable for long-term monitoring. While gel electrodes are a popular alternative due to their non-invasive nature, they have their drawbacks such as the potential for allergic reactions and difficulty in washing off. Additionally, the signal quality decreases when the gel dries out, making them less suitable for long-term monitoring.

Dry electrodes have emerged as an attractive option for neonatal aEEG recording in the near future. This novel technology is non-invasive and does not require the application of conductive gel, thus allowing faster electrode placement, removal, and washing. Studies on adults have shown that dry electrodes are more comfortable and produce signals of sufficient quality, making them a preferred option over needle and gel electrodes (Hinrichs et al., 2020; Ng et al., 2022).

Automated analysis of aEEG traces. Automated seizure detection is an essential aspect of aEEG monitoring in the NICU, while the current seizure detection software used in the WKZ is prone to inaccuracies. To enhance its accuracy and reliability, there is a need to incorporate state-of-the-art techniques, such as deep neural networks, which have demonstrated significant improvements in seizure detection performance compared to traditional methods (Olimi et al., 2021). To ensure trust and transparency in the detection process (Kompa et al., 2021), it is crucial to provide confidence levels (Borovac et al., 2022) and specify the channels used for detection (Isaev et al., 2020). This will enable nurses (and other clinicians) to focus their attention to the parts of the recording that require more scrutiny, thereby increasing efficiency in everyday clinical practice.

To minimize false alarms caused by artifacts, an improved artifact detection software should be incorporated alongside the seizure detection software. Furthermore, to help nurses interpret aEEG recordings, the monitoring system should include other quantitative features such as inter-burst intervals, spectral power, and multiscale entropy (Wang et al., 2023).

Improved monitoring system. In addition to automated analysis, an improved aEEG monitoring system should also offer remote access to address the shortage of aEEG expertise in NICUs (Dilena et al., 2021). This would enable experienced clinicians to monitor patients remotely, which is especially helpful when they cannot be physically present at the NICU. Remote access also allows for a more efficient organization of the

NICU, where nurses can check the aEEG monitoring system from a central station without walking to the monitors.

To accommodate the busy environment of the NICU, the monitoring system should allow users to record past events, such as feeding, in addition to real-time recordings. This is important for later review and interpretation of the aEEG traces. For example, if the infant is moved to another bed, the recording may contain artifacts that do not reflect the electrocortical activity.

To simplify the use of the overall monitoring system in the NICU, it would be beneficial if aEEG monitors could be integrated with other monitoring devices, such as NIRS (Bonifacio and Van Meurs, 2019). This would reduce the number of displays in the crowded NICU, prevent duplication of patient information, and decrease the likelihood of human error.

There are several monitoring systems available on the market that include some of these desired features. For instance, *nēo* (eemagine Medical Imaging Solutions GmbH, Germany) was specifically designed for use in a neonatal hospital environment. This system has automated aEEG pattern analysis (e.g., bursting activity and seizures) and allows the recording of an eight-channel EEG. In addition, there are also more generic EEG monitoring systems that offer neonatal functionalities, e.g., StratusEEG (Kvikna Medical ehf., Iceland), Neurofax EEG-1200 (Nihon Kohden Corporation, Tokyo), and NEUROWERK (Micromed S.p.A., Italy).

4.3. Limitations

The present work has several limitations. As the data was collected from a single center with a specific focus on neonatal neurology, our findings might not be generalized to nurses from other places or nurses with different backgrounds. Future research should include more nurses from different hospital settings. Response bias might have existed because the interviews were conducted in English, however, the mother tongue of the interviewed nurses was Dutch. Therefore, the answers might have been more exhaustive if the interviews had been conducted in Dutch. Additionally, several nurses who were unable to speak English did not join the interviews, probably causing sample bias. Finally, due to the nature of the qualitative analysis, a few answers that were hard to merged into a theme were excluded (as *outliers*), which might cause information loss.

5. Conclusion

Nurses exhibit a significant disparity in aEEG proficiency. Despite this, they have affirmed the usefulness of aEEG in several clinical indications in the NICU, particularly in detecting seizures. Nonetheless, the accuracy of the current automated seizure detection software requires improvement. Furthermore, the (minimally) invasive nature of needle electrodes sometimes deters nurses from advocating for prolonged aEEG monitoring of very small infants.

Nurses are key players in aEEG monitoring. Equipping them with sufficient aEEG knowledge and efficient monitors can substantially improve brain function monitoring for infants and, consequently, the overall care in the NICU. To build nurses' expertise, we recommend implementing systematic training, holding regular case-based discussions, and developing portable reference tools. To further improve the monitoring system, novel electrodes, remote access, advanced automated analysis algorithms, and a user-friendly graphical interface are necessary.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Xiaowan Wang: Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data curation, Writing - Original draft, Writing- Reviewing and Editing.

Ana Borovac: Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Formal

analysis, Investigation, Data curation, Writing- Original draft, Writing - Reviewing and Editing.

Agnes van den Hoogen: Methodology, Resources, Writing - Reviewing and Editing, Supervision.

Maria Luisa Tataranno: Resources, Writing - Reviewing and Editing, Supervision.

Manon J. N. L. Benders: Resources, Writing - Reviewing and Editing, Supervision.

Jeroen Dudink: Conceptualization, Methodology, Resources, Writing - Reviewing and Editing, Supervision, Project administration.

Ethical statement

The current study did not fall within the scope of the Medical Research Involving Human Subjects Act (abbreviation in Dutch: WMO) since participants involved in this study were not exposed to procedures or treatment and did not follow a certain behavioral strategy. This study was carried out following the Good Clinical Practice principles. All participants were verbally informed about the objectives of the current study and its voluntary and anonymous nature.

Funding source

This work was supported by the European Commission [Grant agreement number: EU H2020 MSCA-ITN-2018-#813483, Integrating Functional Assessment measures for Neonatal Safeguard (INFANS)].

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnn.2023.08.003>.

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